

Abstract

Climate change in the recent times has made a considerable impact on the glacier lifecycle in the Himalayan region. Geologically young and fragile, the Himalayas are sensitive to even minor changes in the climatic system. Warming in various parts of the Himalayan region has been observed between 0.15°C and 0.60°C per decade, which is very high as compared to the mean global warming rate of 0.74° C per 100 years. Consequent to this temperature increase, the Himalayan glaciers have been retreating, which has resulted into the formation, expansion and disappearance of various types of glacial lakes. The dangerous lakes among these pose threat to downstream community and infrastructure. In this study an attempt has been made to understand the dynamics of glacial lakes in the Himalayan region through a meta-analysis of peer-reviewed scholarly literature for a period of 2001-2020. The study has found that glacial lakes in the study region are increasing in number and expanding rapidly as the Glacier Lake Outburst Floods (GLOFs) are becoming common. The expansion rates of proglacial lakes connected to glaciers and moraine-dammed lakes is faster than other type of lakes. Findings from area change analysis in the study region conducted by various researchers reveal that a number of expanding glacial lakes can emerge as potential sites for GLOFs, hence need immediate monitoring and observation. Geospatial techniques coupled with field investigations have been found as a potent tool for mapping the evolution and propagation of GLOF hazards resulting from shrinkage of glaciers and lake expansion. Further, the satellite-based remote sensing has been found as an excellent tool for GLOF management as well as reconstruction of a previous GLOF event and predict its future outburst potential. The idea of this study has been derived from the increased incidence of GLOF events in the Himalayan region. This study will help in better understanding of glacial lake expansion and provide scope for future research in devising risk management action plans of potential GLOFs by selecting expanding glacial lakes as case studies.

Keywords: Climate change; Glacier recession; Glacial Lake expansion; GLOFs; Risk management.